

Spectrophotometric and Conductometric Studies of Metal Complexes of 3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-Sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno. Part V. Nickel Complex

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Nickel forms a yellow, water-soluble complex with 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno with an absorbance peak at 420 m μ . The pH range of constant maximum absorbance is between 3.8 and 5.9. The molecular extinction coefficient is 1.04×10^3 at 425 m μ . The formula of the complex, established spectrophotometrically, is NiR₂ (R = reagent), whereas conductometrically NiR₃ is also indicated. The dissociation constant of NiR₂ at 25° is 3.56×10^{-11} and the free energy of the formation of the complex is -14.25 kcal./mole.

3-Hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno forms a yellow, water-soluble complex with nickel. The complex formation is almost instantaneous and the colour intensity remains unaltered even after 24 hours. It is stable to wide temperature variations. The optimum pH range is between 3.8 and 5.9, where the selectivity of the reagent is fairly low. Hence this reagent does not offer any good method for the colorimetric estimation of nickel. The complex formation has been studied at 425 m μ , where the absorbance by the reagent is negligible.

In previous parts of the series¹, the formulas of palladium, molybdenum, copper, and iron complexes were studied. In the present investigation the formula of nickel complex has been established spectrophotometrically, using Job's continued variation method², slope-ratio method³, and molar ratio method⁴. The empirical formula has been found to be NiR₂. The chelate structure may be represented as:

Conductometrically, besides NiR₂, NiR₃ is also indicated.

EXPERIMENTAL

A standard nickel ammonium sulphate (Anala, B.D.H.) solution was prepared and was further diluted to provide $M \times 10^{-3}$ nickel solution. Reagent solution, buffer solutions, instruments, etc. were the same as described in Part I¹.

Spectral Characteristics of Nickel Complex.—Nickel solution ($M \times 10^{-3}$, 4 ml) and the reagent solution ($M \times 10^{-2}$, 4 ml) were taken in a 50 ml flask. Suitable quantities of 10% HCl and 10% sodium acetate were added so that the pH after dilution was at about 5. Absorbance was measured, using reagent solution of the above strength and pH as blank.

1. *This Journal*, 1953, **35**, 542, 859; 1959, **36**, 263; 1960, **37**, 117.
2. *Ann. chim.*, 1928, **2**, 9, 113.
3. Harvey and Manning, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1950, **72**, 4488.
4. Yoe and Jones, *Ind. Eng. Chem., Anal. Ed.*, 1944, **16**, 111.

The complex showed maximum absorbance at 420 m μ . 425 m μ was, however, considered as suitable wave length for all subsequent work as at this wave length the reagent had no absorbance and water could be used as a blank solution.

Effect of pH.—Solutions containing the same concentrations of nickel and the reagent were prepared at different pH values and their absorbance was measured at 425 m μ . The range of constant maximum absorbance was from pH 3.8 to 5.9.

Rate of Reaction and Stability of the Complex.—The full colour development of the nickel complex was almost instantaneous and there was no difference in absorbance taken after 24 hours.

Effect of Temperature.—Samples were heated on a water bath to 85°, cooled to room temperature, and absorbance was measured after making up the volume. There was no difference in the absorbance of this sample and that prepared at room temperature. The complex was thus stable over a wide range of temperature variations.

Nature of the Complex Formed.—In a set of experiments, mixtures containing varying proportions of nickel: reagent were prepared and the optical densities at different wave lengths in each case measured. In all the cases, the maximum absorption occurred at 420 m μ , thus indicating formation of only one complex with the reagent responsible for the colour³.

Composition of the Complex

Job's Method.—A series of solutions was prepared from $M \times 10^{-3}$ of the metal and the reagent in which the ratios of nickel to reagent varied from 1:11 to 11:1. The pH was kept at about 5.0. Absorbance was measured at 425 and 430 m μ . Fig. 1 shows the curves obtained by applying this method. The maxima at 4:8 ratio of nickel to reagent indicate the formation of NiR₄.

FIG. 1

Slope-ratio Method.—The concentration of the variable component was varied from $2 \times 10^{-4} M$ to $14 \times 10^{-5} M$ in presence of the excess concentration of $5 \times 10^{-4} M$ of the constant component. The pH of the solutions was kept at about 5.6. Fig. 2 shows the measured absorbance at $425 m\mu$ plotted against the concentration of the variable component. The slopes of the two straight lines provide nickel: reagent ratio as 1:2.

Molar Ratio Method.—A series of solutions was prepared at pH 5.6, as described earlier, and varying amounts of equimolar solutions of the reagent were added such that the mole ratio of nickel to reagent was from 1:1 to 1:15. Fig. 3 (curve a) shows the molar ratio of nickel to reagent for constant maximum absorbance as 1:6. By adding 1 ml of 1M-KCl solution, a break was obtained (Fig. 3, curve b) at a ratio of two moles of reagent to one mole of nickel. KCl apparently suppresses the dissociation of the complex by bringing in an increase in the ionic strength of the solution.

Conc. of variable component ($M \times 10^5$).
FIG. 2. Ni complex by slope ratio.
a: Ni varying. b: Reagent varying.

FIG. 3. Ni complex by molar ratio.

Conductometric Method.—The method was the same as described in Part IV¹. The formation of two complexes, NiR_2 and NiR_3 , was indicated during the course of the reaction. Spectrophotometrically only the former complex is indicated. Hence it is likely that the yellow complex, giving absorbance peak at $420 m\mu$, has the composition NiR_2 .

DISCUSSION

The dissociation of the complex may be written as:

where C is the concentration of the complex and α is the degree of dissociation. The dissociation constant, K , is given by the equation:

$$K = \frac{\alpha C \times (2 - \alpha C)^2}{C(1 - \alpha)} = \frac{4\alpha^3 C^2}{1 - \alpha}$$

From curve *a*, Fig. 3:

$$\alpha = \frac{E_m - E_a}{E_m} = \frac{0.24 - 0.20}{0.24} = 0.167$$

(where the terms have their usual significance). The concentration C of the complex is equal to the total concentration of nickel, which is $4 \times 10^{-3} M$.

By substituting these values in the above equation, the value of K at 25° comes to 3.56×10^{-11} . Hence the stability constant, K' , is equal to 2.81×10^{10} .

The standard free energy of formation of the complex from nickel sulphate and 3-hydroxy-1-*p*-sulphonatophenyl-3-phenyltriazeno is calculated from the relation:

$$\Delta F^\circ = RT \ln K$$

and works to -14.25 kcal./mole at 25° .

Molecular extinction coefficient, ϵ , is equal to the slope of the straight line 'a' in Fig. 2 and is equal to 1.04×10^5 .

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